

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NSEREKO****FIRST NAME: GODFREY****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Information about this Response Paper:**

I used US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

I used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

I used Zotero to insert references

I used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

I used MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 software

Concepts for the Response Paper:

1. Preparing for academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7–10)
2. Writing the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10–12)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12–14)
4. Understanding punctuation marks and their usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16–23)
5. Comparing American and British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25–32)

INTRODUCTION TO DOCTORAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Starting this academic journey at a doctorate level has ignited mixed feelings within me. I will argue that whereas this journey is not easy, the concepts I will discuss will lighten the burden and anxiety of academic writing. In truth, the course material for this first period has explained many underlying principles behind the English I have used for decades. Some explanations, rules of thumb, and unlearned advice will open my doors to a successful academic life. This is my first response paper under the Euclid University doctorate program, and I will try my best to apply much of the new knowledge gained in this course. In the response paper, the following concepts will be discussed: preparing for academic writing, writing the paper, some rules of thumb for writing a paper, understanding punctuations and their usage, and comparing American and British English.

2) PREPARING FOR ACADEMIC WRITING

Not preparing to write is preparing to fail in writing. It does not matter whether writing is for academic, professional, or even fictional reasons; preparation is necessary for a thoroughly written piece of work. In academic circles, such as at Euclid University, where the overall writing goal is to advance academically and make novel contributions to the body of knowledge, my writing preparations may focus a lot on not only understanding the academic requirements but also extensively looking for answers to questions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). As a scholarly author, looking for answers to hypotheses and finding much-needed evidence to support such answers will require me to be at the top of my game to realize success in academic writing. I will discuss two key components of preparation for academic writing: avoiding procrastination and researching the topic.

Procrastination avoidance may be one of the best ingredients for successful academic writing. Procrastination can become habitual as a writer keeps making excuses and postponing a task, and the sooner the tasks pile up, the more it may overwhelm that person. When I examine the Euclid University program, such as the doctorate I am undertaking, there is a minimum weekly requirement of fifteen hours dedicated to the course – which involves writing and its preparation - and it is by avoiding postponing tasks that course goals can be realized. Cleenewerck and Gulma further stress, "Early start-up: It is best to start as early as possible. One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate" (7). The above quote stresses the importance of starting now rather than later because successful writing will require more than just writing (there are other aspects, such as reading and thinking), which means time is needed. Over the years of academic life, I have fought procrastination vice by setting individual targets on both macro and micro scales: creating daily to-do lists of academic writing goals to lead to the attainment of the greater goal of a well-written paper in record time. As part of adequate preparation for academic writing, creating essay plans and crafting reading timetables is important (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 8). Once time is blocked off for academic writing, any author can have the capacity to tackle the second aspect of preparation: researching the topic of interest.

Extensive research is vital in academic writing. Before writing, I need to have a firm and informed understanding of the topic of interest. Reading and thinking should form an integral part of this quest for knowledge to answer some key questions on what information on the topic is available, whether the available information provides the same arguments for or against my research question, and what innovative ideas I can consider as I frame my paper. Without thinking and reading about my topic, how will I answer questions that I am not even specific other authors have not addressed? So, it is not enough just to read about the topic; thinking about it is equally important since both aspects support an extensive understanding of the idea. It is noteworthy that whereas reading will expose me to new and emerging evidence on my topic of interest, thinking will broaden my knowledge of such identified ideas (creative thinking) and pinpoint areas of focus in the ideas to guide my writing (critical thinking) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9).

3) **WRITING THE PAPER**

No work is done in writing if no writing has been done; after all, how shall we even prove that any work has been done? As an upcoming author, writing a paper is essential for my academic and personal fulfillment. Writing is very fulfilling because I will only feel that my preparations were worthwhile after writing about everything I have researched. The beauty of writing after excellent preparation is that you will be amazed by your work. In this section, I will share what I call the 3Rs to successfully writing an academic paper: Record, Retard, and Right! These steps are not linear but rather continuously interactive.

a) Record

As a first step, making a record (the first R) of whatever is available in the form of a draft zero is imperative. Although the sequence of the whole paper may not be accurate at this time, it is pertinent that ideas remain coherent and focused on the topic as the writing progresses. The course material for this response paper guides that the primary focus should be on writing a substantial body of the paper (a standard essay has three main parts: introduction, body, and conclusion), which comprises effective paragraphs (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). I agree with the proposed format of starting with the body and building complete paragraphs, one at a time, as I am doing while writing this because the body is the building block that will guide both the introduction and the conclusion. Also, I can keep track of the fact that the introduction section of my paper informs the body while the body guides the findings I will deduce at the end.

Understanding the role and format of the parts of a paper is an important discussion in this section. As already mentioned above, the structure of an essay proposed by Euclid University is comprised of three sections: an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. Whereas the introduction sets the write-up tone with a generalized to specific flow into the body and discussion, the conclusion will pick key issues from the preceding parts and make specific to generalized inferences on the topic and its possible contribution to the body of knowledge (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10).

b) Retard

The second R for “retard” entails allowing a reasonable time lag between writing sessions. Writing a paper in one go is difficult and complicated, and not advisable. Imagine writing this response paper and recording all the concepts (and their inherent discussions) in one go; there is a likelihood that some aspects of the write-up will not be accorded the attention and detail they deserve! The course pack for this period suggests that at least two days should be allowed before a draft can be given another look (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 8,11). I argue that whereas this proposed timeline seems convenient, a much shorter time frame (say, giving a second look overnight) can also be workable in time-limited instances. In circumstances like my own, where I must study and work simultaneously, any available time for study is very precious. Hence, spending all two days without looking at

a draft is unrealistic. Allowing time lag between drafts should be a continuous process, not just a one-off. Whenever a draft is updated, I allow a time-lapse to give room for a fresh perspective the next time I look at that paper. Fresh ideas, arguments, and even additional information can be generated and added to enrich my drafts as I go along. By the time I have a final draft ready, I will have had considerable intermissions between working drafts. It is important to note that this step (Retard) works hand in hand with the first step (Record) to achieve a fruitful write-up.

c) Right

The aspect of Right (the third R) means that successful academic writing must be within the confines of the provided or acceptable instructions or guidelines. It is not enough to write, review, and rewrite: the instructions for the write-up must be rightly followed. A key illustration of this phenomenon is the doctorate academic writing at Euclid University. Each course instruction clearly stipulates how to write, how and when to cite, which type of world English to use, which templates to use for different assignments, which style guides are allowed, and even recommended software to support the writing. The acceptable writing format and rules must be used consistently throughout the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). I will discuss some of the elements of proper writing (such as punctuation and their usage, making references, etc.) in subsequent concept areas of this response paper.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

Every academic writer ought to understand and put into practice some generally acceptable principles that relate to scholarly writing. This concept of rules of thumb is particularly important to me because, despite decades of writing English, I have realized in the past few weeks that there is still a lot to learn. I believe that the key considerations I will discuss below are not exhaustive but provide a firm foundation for the successful writing of this response paper. In fact, I had to make sure that I read these rules of thumb before embarking on this response paper for the first period.

Firstly, a main idea, point, or question is important for every paper. You will find many names like thesis, theme, and research question, among others, but the principle remains the same: every paper should have something particular to focus on. Cleenewerck and Gulma advise that in the absence of a thesis, the onus is on the author of the paper to create one, and this thesis must be mentioned as early as possible at the beginning of the paper (13). I agree that the thesis should be fronted early because this will ignite the interest of whoever is reading or reviewing the work and make them quickly understand what the paper is about. Many times, readers and reviewers of academic work are extremely busy and have limited time, and the earlier they understand the focus of the paper, the better it is for the writer. Importantly, as a writer, having my question laid out from the onset paves the way for clarity and maintains focus so that I can keep aligned with my research topic. Without a main idea clearly outlined, I am constantly diverted into other topics that keep coming up as I write, hence the need for the main idea.

Secondly, always get to the point when writing. If a writer has keenly done his research, reading, and thinking around the topic, there should be no reason to beat about the bush but rather to get to the issue you wish to write about. I have been and continue to be a victim of this shortcoming; I am hopeful that this writing exposure will help me improve by the day. Whenever sweeping generalizations are used during writing, it raises suspicions that perhaps the writer has not researched the topic well and they are trying to use general statements to fill the space (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). Whereas I may agree that this is sometimes the case, I would also argue that sometimes vocabulary limitations hinder getting straight to the point. As a writer, then, I have a duty to practice being on point continuously.

Just as difficult to achieve as the previous point, writing clearly while making the work interesting is a must-have for academic writing. To write clearly sounds easy but not yet: it is one of my greatest nightmares. At one point during high school, I used to write with a huge dictionary by my side so that I could get complex vocabulary words or phrases to use; at least, that is what I believed writing clear and interesting work meant. I have been offered some guidance on how to write clearly by using short sentences that should not be too long (like more than three lines long), although that is still a challenge (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). Also, to improve my clarity in writing, I need to work on using appropriate words in the right circumstances and for the right audiences. For example, as a diplomat in the medical field, I must be very keen on the message I put out to non-medical audiences to be sure I am not using vocabulary they would not understand. On the issue of keeping the work interesting while writing, care should be taken to avoid using the same words constantly, use relevant adverbs and adverbial phrases, and always engage transition statements to keep the reader or reviewer interested in the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13).

Avoiding plagiarism is a rule of thumb for any academic writer. When preparing to write a paper, much effort is put into reading and researching the topic of interest; all that material is not the author's work and, therefore, should be cited (except for a few instances where the same information is found ubiquitously). For every piece of work that I read and make inferences, I must cite that work. However, I should not misuse this citation guidance and start to copy and paste other authors' work into my paper and be happy about it. The best practice when reading is to identify the relevant material about the topic as already discussed above; read the material and take note of the citations or references; examine if you understand what you have read and establish your arguments concerning the material; and write only what you think is meaningful to the discussion on the research topic (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). Writing in this age has become simplified on plagiarism checking as there is available software to support this analysis. Therefore, plagiarism should be a non-occurrence for a focused and committed writer like me.

Reading the work out loud is another interesting rule of thumb. Whereas this may sound obvious or unimportant, I will argue that by reading out the work aloud to oneself (perhaps in the mirror) or to another party, I will be able to tell if my work makes sense and also identify the areas of improvement. Additionally, I have to ascertain whether the arguments I am making are coherent and make sense (and will not make me look like a fool to others) to whoever might interface with the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,

13). Moreover, because whatever is written ought to be read, reading out the work aloud offers an opportunity to critically and creatively transform the paper into a masterpiece. These generally accepted rules of thumb will continue to be valuable ingredients in my writing, both academic and professional, for decades to come.

5) UNDERSTANDING PUNCTUATION MARKS AND THEIR USAGE

Writing is critical, but what would writing be like without the right punctuation [yes, you got me right on the statement because it does not have the right punctuation: a question mark!]. Punctuation marks make writing more meaningful, the work becomes more understandable, and they can also help in expressing the right feeling and/or tone of language whenever used. By changing the punctuation, I can easily change the sentence's meaning. In this concept, I will explore – though not exhaustively – how, when, and where to use common punctuations like apostrophes, bullet points, brackets, colons and semicolons, full stops, question marks, and exclamation marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16)

An apostrophe will generally apply in two situations: where letters in a word are omitted and situations to portray possession. I will use the following illustrations to explore the use of apostrophes: *Don't lift Liz's shoes because they are heavy (part 1)* versus *Do not lift the shoes of Liz because they are heavy (part 2)*. Regarding possession, I used an apostrophe in part one to indicate that the shoes belonged to Liz. This usage is common for all nouns and pronouns that do not end in s; however, for nouns that end in s or z where pronunciation is likely to cause confusion, the apostrophe use can be sidestepped, as shown in part 2 by changing how the sentence is constructed (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16). Looking at usage in contractions, part 1 has a contracted first word (Don't), but this is overcome in part 2 when I use the full word. Euclid University writing guidelines advise that contractions should be avoided in academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 17). I agree that contractions are unnecessary, especially if I want my writing to remain clear and unambiguous.

Brackets are punctuations that can be round, square, or angled in nature, and each of these serves a specific purpose in writing. As a doctorate student, I may not routinely interface with angle brackets as they are used in technical contexts. But I am likely to find curly brackets utilized during the review of my work by course instructors (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 17). I will use round brackets more commonly because they are interchangeable with commas and dashes when dealing with non-defining phrases in a statement. I will use the following list of sentences to illustrate the interchangeable use of round brackets, commas, and dashes without changing the sentence's meaning:

- Godfrey Nsereko, popularly known as the Crazy Doc in motorsport circles, is a humble international public health guru;

- Godfrey Nsereko - popularly known as the Crazy Doc in motorsport circles - is a humble international public health guru; and
- Godfrey Nsereko (popularly known as the Crazy Doc in motorsport circles) is a humble international public health guru.

From the above example, round brackets will be popular. I have also used the example to illustrate the use of bullet points as punctuations: they are used to write a list whose punctuation largely depends on the nature of the sentence. In this instance where bullet points are complete sentences, I have used semicolons and the right conjunctions to link and finalize the last bullet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 17). Away from bullet points, care should be taken to put the right punctuation whenever using brackets and maintain the intended meaning. If the phrase in brackets is a complete statement, then the punctuation should be put before the closing bracket; putting the punctuation outside the brackets means the phrase inside the brackets is not complete.

Colons and semicolons for punctuation heavily depend on the logical connection between the phrases that make up the sentence. When a statement has two parts that are logically connected (the first speaks directly to the second), a colon is the preferred punctuation choice. Otherwise, a semicolon works properly in the absence of that logical connection. I have been having this confusion: when to use a colon (this is the right use of the colon because the second part of the sentence explains the confusion in the first part). It is still not easy to determine logical connections between phrases; I am likely to make these errors in the future (this is the correct use of the semicolon because the two phrases do not have a logical connection) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 18). One aspect that was not brought out in the course material for this period is the maintenance of a sentence case format after the colon or semicolon; I believe this is a crucial piece of information to include for consideration when using colons and semicolons because the sentence remains the same despite having the punctuation.

Unlike other punctuations whose use is rather straightforward, the comma is rather complex, and because of this, many concepts, such as comma splicing and the Oxford comma, emerged. The use of the comma must take into precise consideration the context and intended meaning of the sentence. Cleenewerck and Gulma explore using commas to separate defining and non-defining information within a sentence; however, I argue that whether a phrase is defining or non-defining is largely subjective and content-specific (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 19). The application of the comma must tally closely with the intended meaning and the avoidance of confusion. One aspect I found interesting when using commas is its divergent application for multiple qualitative and classifying adjectives. For example, the following statements are both correctly punctuated: he held a big, juicy mango in his gigantic, sweaty hands, and he held a big red mango in his large black hands (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 20). This example depicts the complexity of applying commas as punctuation marks, and as a writer, I must be alert.

Finally, every sentence must end with either a full stop, an exclamation mark, or a question mark. Exceptions to this rule apply to writing titles where a full stop should not be added at the end of the statement. This is an exception, which I have probably applied

during my writing without understanding the underlying principle. Question marks should be carefully applied where a direct question is asked and not in reported speech scenarios (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22). In conclusion of this section, I can say that punctuation is one of the cornerstones for effective and successful academic writing.

6) COMPARING AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

In this academic journey where the medium of exchange is English, I will encounter world English and its variations. Standard American English (American English) and standard British English (British English) are the most common variations I shall encounter in this academic writing process. It is important to be able to understand the differences between the two and appreciate how and where they can be applied in writing. In this section, I will explore some issues to guide when choosing which type of English to use when writing a particular paper and understand some peculiar differences between American and British English in academic writing.

Firstly, identifying the proposed type of English is important before starting to write. Organizations and entities have taken time to set guidelines and recommendations on which English to use under what writing style. Cleenewerck and Gulma allude to the increasing use of American English worldwide over British English, and this relates to the noticeable dominance of American political, social, and technological advances over the decades (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). As an author, I have a duty to look out for what the organization's guidelines provide on which English type to use.

Secondly, for writing purposes, the focus should be on getting the spelling, grammar, and punctuation right in relation to the type of English being used. There are some English words that carry the same spelling but are pronounced differently in American and British English: these should not be a focus when writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 26). Getting the spellings right for words that differ across English variations is critical. I have always struggled with the word "centre" when using Microsoft Office because the software always shows me the correct spelling is "center." It is at this point of my learning that it makes sense that choosing the type of English to use from the outset is very important for writing. The software can detect this anomaly because it defaults to American English. A punctuation scenario using inverted commas or quotation marks depending on the English variation. Whereas the quote 'John is a Baptist' is correct in British English, it should be written as "John is a Baptist" in American English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 32). These are important yet common mistakes that can have far-reaching impacts on a paper.

Lastly, writing dates and observing date formats are critical when dealing with American and British English. In February this year, I missed a significant engagement because I thought the same had been planned for March. When I received the invitation date of 02.03.2024, I interpreted it as the 2nd of March (in British English format). However, it was supposed to be the 3rd of February (in American English format). This example underscores the importance of being careful about dates and how they are written in either type of English. In conclusion, the key differences between American and British English

should be appreciated, and appropriate mechanisms should be implemented to ensure consistent writing in the chosen or preferred variation.

7) **CONCLUSION**

Having examined some of the key concepts in the course pack and understood their importance and usage, I am optimistic that a firm foundation has been set to drive successful academic writing. These principles will continue to apply in all my future writing, and with continuous practice, I will emerge as a great academic writer.

REFERENCES

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